

ON A RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN REFRACTIVE INDEX AND SURFACE TENSION.

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Lorentz and Lorenz equation for molecular refraction has been combined with Sugden's parachor equation. The resulting equation $\frac{n^2-1}{n^2+2} = \frac{R}{P} \gamma^{\frac{1}{2}}$ is found to be correct even when R and P are calculated from their corresponding atomic and configurational constants. This equation has been shown to be successful in calculating values of surface tensions with the knowledge of those of refractive indices and *vice versa*.

Lorentz and Lorenz derived the equation,

$$\frac{n^2-1}{n^2+2} \cdot \frac{M}{d} = R$$

where n is the refractive index, d , the density and M , the molecular weight of a liquid and R , the molecular refraction. It was also shown that R is an additive quantity and it can be calculated by adding up the atomic refractions and refractions due to various linkages present in the molecule.

Sugden's parachor equation (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 128, 1177)

$$P = \frac{M}{d} \gamma^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

where M is the molecular weight, d , the density and γ , the surface tension and P , a constant, which is additive in the same way as molecular refraction, is also a well known equation.

These two equations can be combined to give

$$\frac{n^2-1}{n^2+2} = \frac{R}{P} \gamma^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

Since R and P can both be calculated from atomic constants, a knowledge of surface tension can give refractive index and *vice versa*. To test this relationship $\frac{n^2-1}{n^2+2}$ and $\frac{R}{P} \gamma^{\frac{1}{2}}$ were calculated in cases of some eighty organic liquids listed below :—

Benzene, ether, chloroform, aniline, acetone, toluene, carbon tetrachloride, nitrobenzene, methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, formic acid, acetic acid, propionic acid, propyl alcohol, acetonitrile, acetophenone, acetyl chloride,* acetylene tetrabromide, acetylene tetrachloride, ethyl acetate, ethylaniline,* ethyl benzoate, ethyl butyrate, ethyl *isobutyrate*, ethylene bromide, ethylene chloride, ethyl formate, ethylidene chloride, ethyl iodide, ethyl propionate, amyl acetate, anisol, benzaldehyde, benzonitrile, benzophenone, bromobenzene, *cyclohexane*, *paracymol*, diethylamine, diethylketone, diethyl oxalate, di-*isobutylamine*, dipropylamine, furfural, ethylene-glycol, hexane, mesitylene,* methyl acetate, methyl ethyl ketone, methylaniline, methyl benzoate, *o*-bromotoluene, *n*-& *isobutyric acid* *n*-& *isobutyl alcohol*, allylamine, *isoamyl alcohol*, *isoamylamine*, formamide, normal butylamine, tertiary butylamine, capronitrile,* *isobutylamine*, *isobutyl valerate*, *ortho*-chloroaniline, chlorobenzene, methyl propionate, methyl propyl ketone, nitroethane, nitromethane, *ortho*-nitrotoluene, octane, paraldehyde, phenol, naphthaline, piperidine, propionitrile, propyl acetate, α -picolin, *isocaproic acid*.

Except in case of liquids marked with asterisk the agreement was quite good. Even in cases where the agreement was not so good, the difference did not exceed 3%.

In case of associated liquids also this equation is valid, which shows that both *R* and *P* are affected to the same extent by molecular association.

In Table I a few typical cases, where the agreement is good, have been listed.

TABLE I

Temp.	$\frac{n^2-1}{n^2+2}$	$\frac{R}{P}\gamma^{\frac{1}{3}}$	%Diff.	Temp.	$\frac{n^2-1}{n^2+2}$	$\frac{R}{P}\gamma^{\frac{1}{3}}$	%Diff.
Benzene.				Chloroform.			
8.5°	0.298	0.298		12.5	0.269	0.267	
12.3	0.297	0.297	0.1	18	0.267	0.265	0.7
15	0.296	0.296		22.4	0.266	0.264	
20	0.295	0.294					
Aniline.				Ethyl alcohol			
7.5	0.338	0.335		0	0.226	0.227	
16.4	0.337	0.333	1.0	6.8	0.224	0.226	
20	0.335	0.332		13.3	0.223	0.224	0.5

TABLE II.

Substance.	Temp.	$\frac{n^2-1}{n^2+2}$	$\frac{R}{P} \frac{1}{\gamma^2}$	% Diff.
Toluene	... 14.7	0.294	0.292	0.7
Acetylene tetrabromide	... 20	0.355	0.354	0.3
Ethyl isobutyrate	... 17.8	0.238	0.236	0.8
Ethylene bromide	... 13.5	0.315	0.312	0.9
Ethylene chloride	... 20	0.266	0.268	0.7
Ethylidene chloride	... 20	0.251	0.250	0.4
Ethyl propionate	... 18.4	0.234	0.233	0.4
Anisol	... 21.8	0.301	0.298	1.0
Benzaldehyde	... 17.6	0.317	0.320	0.9
Benzonitrile	... 25.5	0.307	0.307	0.0
Furfural	... 20	0.307	0.307	0.0
Methyl ethyl ketone	... 15.9	0.232	0.230	0.9
Acetylene tetrachloride	... 20	0.290	0.287	1.0
Nitrobenzene	... 39	0.315	0.312	0.9
Ethyl butyrate	... 18	0.239	0.238	0.4
Isobutyric acid	... 20	0.239	0.239	0.0

TABLE III.

Substance.	Temp.	$\frac{n^2-1}{n^2+2}$	$\frac{R}{P} \frac{1}{\gamma^2}$	% Diff.
Carbon tetrachloride	... 20°	0.274	0.270	1.4
Acetonitrile	... 16.5	0.213	0.216	1.4
Acetophenone	... 19.6	0.311	0.306	1.6
Ethylaniline	... 20	0.321	0.315	1.8
Ethyl benzoate	... 20	0.297	0.290	2.4
Ethyl formate	... 20	0.221	0.218	1.3
Formic acid	... 20	0.225	0.222	1.3
Benzophenone	... 53.5	0.340	0.333	2.0
Bromobenzene	... 4.2	0.327	0.331	1.2
cycloHexane	... 16.6	0.257	0.261	1.5
p-Cymol	... 13.7	0.290	0.283	2.4
Di-Isobutylamine	... 19.6	0.248	0.245	1.2
Dipropylamine	... 19.5	0.245	0.242	1.2
Mesitylene	... 17.1	0.293	0.286	2.4
Methylaniline	... 20	0.329	0.322	2.1
Methyl benzoate	... 16.5	0.302	0.298	1.3
Ether	... 15	0.218	0.215	1.4
	... 21.3	0.216	0.213	
Methyl alcohol	... 12.6	0.205	0.208	1.6
	... 18	0.204	0.207	
	... 30	0.201	0.201	
Amyl acetate	... 20	0.243	0.240	1.2
Propionic acid	... 20	0.236	0.233	1.3

The usefulness of this equation will be evident from Table IV where the surface tensions of some liquids have been calculated from the knowledge of their refractive indices.

TABLE IV.

Substance.	Temp	n .	γ (obs.)	γ (calc)	%Diff.
Acetone	... 20°	1'35931	23'09(N ₂)	23'35	1'2
Ethyl acetone	... 20	1'37257	23'60(V)	23'94	1'4
Ethyl alcohol	.. 20	1'36230	22'03(V)	21'92	0'5
Ethyl butyrate	... 18	1'39302	24'44(A)	24'75	1'2
Ethyl iodide	... 20	1'51307	28'10(N ₂)	28'05	0'2
Hexane	... 14'8	1'37800	17'93(V)	18'28	1'9
Methyl acetate	... 20	1'36099	23'84(V)	23'88	0'2
Methyl propyl ketone	... 20'2	1'39946	25'08(V)	25'12	0'2
Octane	... 15'1	1'40070	21'32(V)	21'30	0'1
Acetylene tetrabromide	... 20	1'62772	48'00(N ₂)	48'26	0'6
Nitroethane	... 24'3	1'39007	31'08(V)	31'62	1'8
Diethyl oxalate	... 20	1'41043	32'90(A)	33'33	1'0
Methyl ethyl ketone	... 15'9	1'38071	24'24(V)	24'84	2'4
Nitromethane	... 21'6	1'38133	35'60(N ₂)	35'38	0'5
Ethylidene chloride	... 20	1'41655	23'50(N ₂)	23'99	2'0

The percentage differences between the observed and calculated values of surface tension given in the last column of Table IV seem to be within the limits of experimental error as the values of surface tension found by various authors very often exhibit the percentage difference of the same order amongst themselves.

All the data for this paper have been taken from Landolt Börnstein Tabellen (1923 Edition).

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